

HR1004 was bred through anther culture of CPSLO 17/Skybonnet (F₁). It has high grain quality, wide compatibility, and CMS restoring ability. Protein content is up to 12.9% and amylose content is 17.4%. Grain is long

and thin (length:width ratio is 3.6), and not chalky. When it was crossed with Xie Qin Zhao A or Chang Fei 22 A, the hybrid showed high quality in grain appearance and edibility.

Using androgenesis of indica rice to

induce pollen plantlets and improve varieties is an effective breeding path. Further studies are needed, however, to improve the frequency of green plantlet induction in indica rice. ■

Identification of cytoplasmic male sterile (CMS) sources in rice through reciprocal crosses

Chuanguo Li, Zhongming Cheng, and Weigong Zhong, Food Crops Institute, Jiangsu Academy of Agricultural Sciences, China

Many rice varieties of different origins were crossed during 1988-90. Some seed parents have shown a dramatic cytoplasmic effect on F₁ fertility when crossed with pollen parents.

We used tester parents PAL, 2159, 029, 02428, Ys 8072, Ys 8804, LH422, and Reed rice (Table 1) to make reciprocal crosses in 1991. Each cross was planted in a single row of 15 plants with 25- × 20-cm spacing in Nanjing (32° N). The F₁ pollen fertility was checked.

We observed significant reciprocal difference in both pollen and spikelet fertility in four of the six reciprocal crosses involving PAL as the seed parent (Table 2). A similar difference existed in two of the three crosses involving Reed rice as maternal parent. The six crosses with either PAL or Reed rice cytoplasm were completely sterile in both pollen fertility and seed setting of bagged panicles. The corresponding crosses with either PAL or Reed rice as pollen parents showed normal fertility.

The natural outcrossing rate varied greatly among crosses showing fertility in F₁. The outcrossing rate of PAL/2159 and Reed rice/2159 was high and significantly higher than that of PAL/029, PAL/02428, PAL/Ys 8072, and Reed rice/Ys 8072 (Table 2). Because 2159 seems to have enhanced outcrossing, 2159 may be used as a maintainer to develop PAL and Reed rice CMS lines.

The remaining three reciprocal crosses of PAL/LH422, PAL/Ys 8804, and Reed

Table 1. Characteristics of parents used in crosses.

Parent	Varietal group ^a	Pedigree or origin	Remarks ^b
2159	I	NJ11/IR29	
PAL	I	Palgarh 31-1-3	
Reed rice	I	Reed-like wild rice(?)/IR24	
029	J	Luai//IR8/Nongkeng 58///IR36///ASD7	WC
02428	J	Jipangdao/Pangxiegu	WC
Ys 8072	J	020/729	WC
Ys 8804	J	Nankeng 35/020	WC
LH422	M	Hunan Hybrid Rice Center, China	WC

^aI = indica, J = japonica, M = intermediate. ^bWC = wide compatibility.

Table 2. Pollen fertility and percent seed setting in reciprocal crosses of rice varieties.

Cross	Pollen ^a	Seed setting (%)	
		Bagged panicles	Natural outcrossing
2159/PAL	F	88.63 ± 7.31	85.29 ± 8.13
PAL/2159	CS	0	65.59 ± 7.88
029/PAL	F	72.46 ± 8.91	78.51 ± 7.10
PAL/029	CS	0	16.78 ± 9.01
02428/PAL	F	75.38 ± 7.21	79.18 ± 6.76
PAL/02428	CS	0	10.33 ± 5.72
Ys 8072/PAL	F	68.78 ± 7.83	79.44 ± 3.83
PAL/Ys 8072	CS	0	32.38 ± 15.44
LH422/PAL	F	75.60 ± 6.82	74.38 ± 0.14
PAL/LH422	F	78.23 ± 4.32	72.29 ± 3.83
Ys 8804/PAL	F	74.21 ± 3.78	77.60 ± 5.39
PAL/Ys 8804	F	64.28 ± 8.11	62.23 ± 11.99
2159/Reed rice	F	78.43 ± 3.78	88.01 ± 4.37
Reed rice/2159	CS	0	57.39 ± 4.75
Ys 8072/Reed rice	F	65.32 ± 4.58	68.88 ± 7.48
Reed rice/Ys 8072	CS	0	28.18 ± 13.07
LH422/Reed rice	F	64.21 ± 4.33	63.41 ± 5.62
Reed rice/LH422	F	73.78 ± 5.31	75.32 ± 4.73

^aF = fertile (>90% fertility), CS = completely sterile (<1% fertility).

rice/LH422 were highly fertile (Table 2). Results suggest that LH422 has Rf gene(s) that can restore fertility for PAL and Reed rice sterile cytoplasm, and

Ys 8804 for PAL. CMS sources PAL and Reed rice and the restorers reported in Table 2 seem to be promising material in hybrid rice breeding. ■